

Outcomes

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AD4GD

Research for a FAIR and integrated European Green Deal Data Space

AD4GD. Research for a FAIR and integrated European Green Deal Data Space. Outcomes Booklet

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The content presented in this booklet is the result of the collaborative work of all partners of the AD4GD consortium.

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What is AD4GD?

AD4GD (All Data for Green Deal) conducted research and deployment of key components for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS), guided by the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles.

These components were motivated and validated by **three pilot cases** focused on the main priorities of the European Green Deal in specific locations: monitoring water quality and quantity of small lakes in Berlin, assessing habitat connectivity dynamics in Catalonia, and improving the resolution of Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) air quality maps with urban citizen science.

The main outcomes of AD4GD include:

Uplifting the meaning of Earth observation data and observations. This is achieved by applying semantic enrichment pipelines to data using references to the OGC RAINBOW terms and exposing the data as JSON-LD files or in OGC SensorThings API standard implementations.

Enabling trusted processing of machine learning data in the cloud. This facilitates data processing, but it also guarantees that the results are findable, accessible, trustworthy, and reusable.

Evaluating and testing the use of Eclipse Dataspace Connectors together with OGC APIs for the GDDS. By

deploying several instances of connectors implementing the data space protocol, AD4GD was able to demonstrate secured data exchange among AD4GD partners and other projects.

Demonstrating that newly developed OGC API standards, some of them contributed by project members, can be

added to the GDDS trustworthy implementations accessible through the data space connectors.

In collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects, such as GREAT, FAIRiCUBE, B3, USAGE and SAGE, AD4GD has contributed to shaping the future of the Green Deal Data Space.

The interdisciplinary team behind the outcomes of AD4GD.

What is the Green Deal Data Space?

The Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) is a developing digital environment that will enable the secure and trustworthy exchange of environmental data across the European Union.

The GDDS emerges at the intersection of the European green and digital transitions as one of the common data spaces envisioned by the European Strategy for Data to harness the power of data to achieve the goals of the Green Deal in priority actions like biodiversity preservation, zero pollution, circular economy, climate change mitigation, deforestation reduction, smart mobility and environmental compliance.

Within the data space, a digitally certified data provider is able to

safely transfer high-value and high-quality data with an authorised recipient under a set of commonly agreed rules defined by digital contracts and data licenses. A federated system enables a symmetrical exchange among all the participants in the data space ensuring data sovereignty and the implementation of the FAIR principles.

The Green Deal Data Space benefits businesses, governments, researchers and citizens alike by interconnecting the currently fragmented and dispersed data coming from diverse domains and sources, including private and open data, satellite imagery, Internet of Things sensor data, socioeconomic and citizen generated data.

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Green Deal Data Space for...

Smarter Monitoring of Water Pollution in Small Lakes in Berlin

Authorities can better allocate actions and resources by using observed and forecasted water quality and availability indices.

Berlin's surface is 30% covered by forest and 6% by water. Besides the Spree-Havel river and lake system, there are **more than 300 lakes smaller than 50 hectares distributed throughout its urban fabric**. These lakes serve as freshwater sources, stormwater buffers, biodiversity hotspots, and climate refuges for city residents, but rapid urban densification and increasingly frequent extreme temperature and precipitation events driven by climate change are putting them under growing pressure. Moreover, they suffer from limited monitoring and insufficient maintenance, as they fall outside the scope of the EU Water Framework Directive, and municipal management resources are limited.

AD4GD has produced a set of interconnected services aimed at improving the monitoring of these lakes by developing:

A new satellite-based water quality index called the "Normalized Difference Trophic Index".

Automated integration of citizen science data using CrowdWater App to gather observations and low-cost sensors measurements for consecutive generation of semi-quantitative indicators.

Water quality estimations using in-situ oxygen sensors: time series of six lakes were recorded during the summer seasons of 2024 and 2025.

A water availability prediction model, capable of forecasting water level trends under different precipitation scenarios using machine learning.

Splashboard, a user-centered interface

All data and indices, both raw and processed, are displayed in a graphical user interface called Splashboard, developed jointly with stakeholders in Berlin through a human-centred design process.

The interface displays a map of Berlin along with a searchable catalogue of lakes and their trophic state. When users select a specific lake, they are directed to a dedicated page presenting five key widgets. A metadata widget presents general lake information and an interactive map where users can navigate

between layers of geospatial data. Two-gauge meters display the trophic state and trend indicators. Users can observe historical lake measurements in a statistical time series chart, which includes air and water temperature, precipitation and reference evapotranspiration. Water level forecasts generated by AI models are shown in a predictions' widget. A final widget lets authenticated users contribute with comments or observations related to a lake, and mark a lake as a favourite to quickly access its information.

Screenshot of the Splashboard platform, developed by AD4GD.

Led by

KWB
Kompetenzzentrum
Wasser Berlin

Simplified data flow schema for the water pilot.

Determining trophic status with remote sensing data

There are many Copernicus products based on Sentinel-2 data that determine water properties, including turbidity, chlorophyll content, and water level. AD4GD developed a new index to estimate the trophic status of lakes called the "Normalized Difference Trophic Index". It is calculated by combining three years of data

Citizen taking a picture of a lake through the CrowdWater app.

about the trophic status of the lakes, obtained from the Sentinel-2 L2A product. Trophic growth is determined over an entire growing season. This method was developed using 294 lakes greater than 50 hectares in Brandenburg, Germany. Applying this method to 42 Berlin lakes, AD4GD was able to rank their condition from 2018 to 2024 and identify trends. This can be used, for instance, to evaluate the effects of remediation measures.

Citizen Science as lake monitoring support

On one hand, a method for collecting qualitative data using the pre-existing CrowdWater app, was developed. This app is freely available for registered users. A questionnaire was created in close consultation with Berlin stakeholders, including inquiries about the lake biotope, water quality and water availability. Answers are translated into indicators for assessing water

quality in terms of nutrients, biotope, use, and risk of water scarcity. On the other hand, simple measurements of nutrients and conductivity were carried out by citizens at the lake shore using low-budget tests and sensors. The concentrations of phosphate, nitrite, and ammonium were measured. Volunteers registered as water rangers at KWB and carried out tests at one lake every one to two months. This supports the work of lake managers, who are unable to monitor all lakes regularly.

Estimating water quality with in-situ oxygen sensors

The oxygen concentration in water is directly linked to the trophic status. Algae and aquatic plants typically produce a peak in oxygen concentration during the day and lower concentrations at night. The difference between minimum and maximum oxygen concentrations at the water surface is expected to be

particularly large in lakes with high nutrients levels and high trophic status.

AD4GD installed oxygen sensors at a depth of 20 cm during the summer seasons of 2024 and 2025. Oxygen time series of 6 lakes were recorded. After analysing the data, it was demonstrated that these measurements can provide interesting information when analysed over a long period, but are not suitable for drawing conclusions about the trophic status of small urban lakes through short-term usage.

Locating lakes with potential water shortages

The CrowdWater app can also be used to locate lakes with water shortages and plan interventions. If rainwater is not directed to sewage treatment plants, it can be used locally as a water source for small lakes. To

check this option, a generic stormwater inflow potential was developed to calculate the effective run-off volume of the surrounding areas of all studied lakes. In future calculations, levels of pollution should be considered, as rainwater run-off from urban areas is usually contaminated with pollutants and nutrients, causing problems in lakes.

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Green Deal Data Space for...

Monitoring and optimization of habitat connectivity

Enhancing the workflows for the calculation of functional landscape connectivity for easier decision-making.

Functional landscape connectivity reflects the ability of species to pass through landscape, moving between patches of habitats. Connectivity for animal and plant dispersal is a key consideration when national, regional, and local governments make strategic spatial decisions related to protected areas, industrial and residential zoning, agriculture regulations or land remediation.

Biodiversity conservation, and ecological connectivity, in particular, is a fundamental milestone in global and European policies strategies, from the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2025 to the Convention on Biodiversity post-2020 targets and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

AD4GD has enhanced the calculation of functional landscape connectivity, making it easier for decision makers, in particular by:

Enriching land-use/land-cover maps with datasets from OpenStreetMap and World Database on Protected Areas using the Data4Land tool.

Creating optimized processing workflows to calculate habitat connectivity via Graphab and MiraMon.

Enriching tables and occurrence cubes with data from GBIF, IUCN and ancillary user-defined sources.

Testing machine learning models to predict landscape functional connectivity in future land management scenarios.

BioConnect, a platform for connectivity calculation

All the data and indices are displayed in a graphical user interface called BioConnect, designed using a human-centered design process informed by potential end users.

This tool features a centralized home page with an interactive map that enables users to explore various layers related to land-use, habitat connectivity indexes, species distribution, remote sensing data, infrastructures like roads and railways, rivers and water bodies, cadastral information and historical datasets focused on Catalonia.

BioConnect also equips users with the ability to create scenarios by simulating changes in land-use/land-cover. Users can draw a polygon on the map to represent an area of change and assign it to a new land-use classification. Then, the connectivity index can be recalculated using high or low resolution processing. Users can preview all their saved scenarios, download/upload them as JSON and even process them the same way as before. Once processed, the results are shown in a comparative view displaying the original and the new scenario.

Screenshot of the Bioconnect platform, developed by AD4GD.

Co-led by:

Simplified data flow schema for the biodiversity pilot.

Data4land, a pre-processing tool

Data4Land carries out preliminary analysis of input raster datasets and requests to REST APIs to retrieve vector datasets from OpenStreetMap and World Database on Protected Areas to enrich land-use/land-cover maps. The tool also harmonises and rasterises vector datasets. Data4Land also extracts

Camera trap placed in a tree to observe biodiversity in situ.

biodiversity stressors based on the user configuration to enrich landscape impedance. The processed outputs may be used for subsequent analysis of habitat connectivity in Graphab, MiraMon or other softwares.

Graphab processing and post-processing

The Graphab processing workflow is formed by a Java application; a wrapping main Python script and underlying job, defining the commands which are relevant for local and regional connectivity studies; the configuration files, defining ecological parameters and commands scheduled to run for each case study; and auxiliary Python scripts, to harmonise processing outputs, calculate stats, visualise trends, and access, read, and upload data from/to MinIO. The Graphab application and habitat connectivity indices calculation commands were implemented on Aston University's HPC cluster Nandi, to improve performance.

MiraMon Processing

AD4GD has developed the MiraMon ICT (Index of Terrestrial Connectivity) tool, a stand-alone plugin tool for the MiraMon GIS Software. The original computation of the ICT index was performed using a large number of sequential batch processing commands, making it difficult to manipulate and execute. The new MiraMon ICT calculates the ICT index more efficiently and significantly reducing the execution time.

GBIF2IUCN tool for table enrichment

This tool is used to extract available data for potential subspecies of interest from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and ancillary user-defined sources, and enrich it with spatial raster datasets in several steps. Registration is required to access the relevant data from some of the external services like

the Digital Observatory for Protected Areas. These were made accessible via collaboration with the EU's Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, based at the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC). GBIF2IUCN uses datasets like the species lists, custom conservation information and raster samples, and produces enriched tables and occurrence data cubes.

Biodiversity Machine Learning (ML) Models

AD4GD tested ML models to predict future Functional Landscape Connectivity using existing land-use/land-cover (LULC) data, comparing results to those obtained from the MiraMon software. A trained AI model was employed to reduce the computational cost and processing time required to translate LULC maps into ICT values. While models trained on insufficiently large datasets produced inconclusive results,

the outcomes for the Forest Connectivity Index were sufficiently robust, achieving a drastic reduction in computation time, from weeks to minutes. This suggests that, with adequate training data, AI models can serve as a viable and highly efficient alternative to traditional approaches when evaluating the implications of modifying the landscape.

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Green Deal Data Space for...

Urban air quality monitoring with low-cost IoT sensors

Increasing the density of citizen observation networks to improve the resolution of air pollution insights

The air we breathe is polluted with substances like particulate matter, ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide or carbon monoxide which can originate from natural sources and human activity. According to the WHO, these pollutants present robust evidence of risks for public health. Advocating for adequate air quality is crucial for the Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals. However, air quality monitoring networks are often sparse and unable to provide high-resolution insights. Low-cost sensors represent an interesting opportunity, but their accuracy and reliability remain a recurring challenge.

Led by:

AD4GD has developed a rigorous approach based on machine learning for evaluating the practical usability of citizen science observations of air quality based on IoT sensors. The focus has been set on data from the Sensor.Community network, but the same approach has been applied to several regions in Europe that represent different air quality regimes and unique regional characteristics such as orography, air pollution sources and weather patterns. This has resulted in:

A trustworthiness assessment and harmonisation pipeline that enhances data usability.

Collocation and quality-checking of low-cost sensors, supported by semantic enrichment of data.

ECMWF's Cross Data Store

All the processed data products related to air quality are accessible via ECMWF's Cross Data Store (XDS). The XDS is a federated data access infrastructure that enables users to discover, query, and retrieve environmental datasets from multiple thematic sources through a unified interface.

The air-quality-related gridded data cubes generated by AD4GD, and their metadata, are published in standardized formats within the XDS.

This ensures compliance with FAIR principles and supports integration with other Copernicus data products and services, such as those provided by CAMS or C3S.

Through the XDS, researchers, public agencies, and application developers can seamlessly access harmonised air quality data in combination with complementary geospatial datasets, facilitating cross-domain environmental analysis and decision support.

The air we breathe is polluted with various substances.

Simplified data flow schema for the air quality pilot.

Trustworthiness assessment and harmonisation

The developed data processing and harmonisation pipeline transforms raw, unevenly distributed time series from low-cost IoT air quality sensors into consistent, high-resolution spatiotemporal datasets. This pipeline is essential to ensure that the observational data are

Air pollution in a city environment.

trustworthy, specifically usable, and compatible with downstream workflows such as model validation or exposure mapping, and to facilitate the integration into further applications, such as the ECMWF's Cross Data Store.

The pipeline consists of two tightly coupled stages. Firstly, a trustworthiness assessment and correction, where unreliable or biased data are identified and corrected, and secondly, spatial harmonisation, where the cleaned time series are interpolated into gridded 3D data cubes using kriging techniques. Both stages are built to be modular and scalable, capable of handling large volumes of heterogeneous observations across multiple years and sensor network configurations.

Collocation and quality-checking of low-cost sensors

The low-cost sensors automated

ingestion tool developed in AD4GD enables ingestion and harmonisation data from sensor types not available through other aggregation platforms, like mobile personal devices, and has also facilitates the easy cross-comparison of data from experimentally collocated sensors, to evaluate quality and consistency. The semantic enrichment of the data improves the opportunity to identify which data is genuinely comparable and highlight the need for additional correction steps before data are combined. An example notebook can be explored in GitHub.

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FAIR Components for the Green Deal Data Space

The Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) will consist in a series of building blocks that should comply with the FAIR principles by design. AD4GD developed a comprehensive set of components that respond to various of its requirements and can be exploited for the development of this common

European data space. The AD4GD provider is able to ingest three types of data: vector, sensor and raster. Sensor data and raster data are harmonized via the STApplus and the OpenDataCube respectively. The MinIO component serves as the data repository and GeoNetwork is the metadata catalogue.

AI and machine learning processing create new data for each of the pilot cases. The semantic enrichment pipelines also generate new data relying on the OGC Rainbow and the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM). These two components feed back into the MinIO repository.

The Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) is presented as a way to expose AD4GD data in the GDDS. Open data could also be shared using standard APIs. External providers could also participate in the GDDS using other types of connectors, like the one presented by FACTS. Once the data is exposed in the GDDS, it can be consumed by visualisation tools like TAPIS and Graphical User Interfaces, such as the ones developed in AD4GD for the water pollution and biodiversity pilots. This consumption is conditioned to the negotiation of digital contracts, under the governance of the data owners and based on their policies.

In the figure, the exploitable components are highlighted in orange, while the other components, shown in blue, are either custom-developed by AD4GD or already existing off-the-shelf. All components developed by AD4GD can be found in the project's GitHub (<https://github.com/AD4GD/>)

OGC API Coverages for Open Data Cube

Obstacle

Once an Open Data Cube (ODC) implementation is set up on a computer, accessing the data typically requires running Python or R scripts on that same machine. This can suppose a challenge for users who either lack the technical skills to write such scripts or do not have direct access to the server where the ODC instance is hosted. It can also create some vulnerability to the ODC host server.

Solution

In AD4GD project, a front-end implementation of the OGC API - Coverages has been developed in Python, tailored for the integration with Open Data Cube. This interface acts as a translator between OGC API requests and the underlying Python code, which is executed on the server to retrieve and return the requested data in a standardized way.

Description

A coverage is a way to represent geographic data where each location is associated with a value describing a property such as temperature, humidity, or elevation. The Open Data Cube is a software designed to store multidimensional data, meaning it can hold values across multiple spatial dimensions, as well as temporal, elevation, temperature, or other related properties simultaneously.

To access all or part of this multidimensional data, AD4GD uses the OGC API - Coverages. This web service standard developed by the Open Geospatial Consortium is tailored to facilitate access to coverage data.

Integrating the OGC API - Coverages with the Open Data Cube presents an opportunity to enhance data accessibility and reusability, particularly within the context of data spaces.

Usage in the project

AD4GD managed two different types of data: feature-based data stored in RDF data model, and multidimensional data stored within the Open Data Cube. This approach is particularly relevant in the biodiversity pilot case.

Foreseen applications

The developed Python script is compatible with any Open Data Cube setup, meaning that anyone running an Open Data Cube instance can use this front-end to make their multidimensional data accessible through the OGC API - Coverages.

References

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Semantic Uplift

Obstacle

Implementing the ambitious strategies of the Green Deal require connecting a multitude of heterogeneous services and datasets. Since a single overall solution is not possible, interoperability among components of the GDDS is required, especially at a semantic level.

Solution

AD4GD has enabled semantic interoperability, harmonisation, and enrichment across all the components developed for the GDDS. The approach includes reusing existing and widely utilized ontologies under the framework of the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM) and the establishment of semantic mappings that bridge domain- and source-specific semantic concepts, ensuring reliability and trustworthiness of the data.

Description

The Semantic Uplift component is central to enabling interoperability, harmonisation, and semantic alignment across AD4GD ecosystem. It provides a suite of modular, cloud-hosted semantic services designed to transform heterogeneous datasets into semantically enriched and interoperable resources.

These services support structured alignment with ontologies such as the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM), which is core to the GDDS. Semantic uplift lower entry barriers to streamlined tooling and automation, empowering both technical and non-technical stakeholders to contribute data with minimal configuration, typically requiring only initial mapping to shared vocabularies.

The Semantic Uplift component delivers a comprehensive set of capabilities through integrated

services designed to support semantic interoperability, data harmonisation, and compliance with EU data frameworks. These capabilities are realised through the following key functionalities and tools:

Data Mapping, Harmonisation & Semantic Lifting: transforms heterogeneous datasets into semantically enriched, interoperable formats aligned with the GDIM and its underlying re-used standard models like SOSA/SSN, QUDT, and other ontologies. Based on the use of Linked Data and Knowledge graph technologies, the tool facilitates data harmonisation pipelines, CLI, Web Service, and GUI-based tools for ETL, semantic mapping, transformation, and linking.

Vocabulary Alignment & Semantic Publishing: publishes vocabularies that align datasets related concepts (e.g., observed

properties or sensors) with standard vocabularies and thesauri (e.g. Climate and Forecast standard names, Agrovoc, Essential Variables) to ensure semantic coherence across domains. The tool facilitating this is the **OGC Rainbow Server**, a public registry for publishing and browsing domain-specific vocabularies, mappings, and identifiers with dereferencable URIs

Harmonized data access components: the semantic uplift is able to provide or generate interfaces to access the GDIM harmonized data. This is achieved through access interfaces, such as SPARQL and OGC APIs, and components to generate standard APIs, including the OGC STA generation service that generates STA endpoints automatically from GDIM compliant measurements or observations.

Trusted Data Processing Environments: cloud-hosted environments are provided to execute semantic uplift workflows, including annotation and transformation pipelines, using **DPI Cloud Services**. These, support CSVW, JSON Schema, SHACL validation, and storage in semantic triple stores such as Virtuoso.

Usage in the project

Semantic uplift was applied in all three AD4GD pilots to harmonise local datasets with the GDIM. Each pilot implemented harmonisation semantic pipelines, leveraging shared vocabularies and mapping specifications. In particular, the biodiversity pilot used SPARQL mappings and EV vocabularies to semantically transform species simulation data (e.g., BES-SIM AIM) into interoperable RDF representations. However, the water and air quality pilots employed YAML-based mappings

Annotating CSVW columns with OGC RAINBOW terms.

and custom vocabularies processed via DPI pipelines and published through the OGC Rainbow server, ensuring semantic traceability and alignment with European standards

Foreseen applications

The semantic uplift services and tools developed by AD4GD can be exploited for the development of the GDDS. All the functionalities can be replicated and reused in other environments according to the user needs.

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Green Deal Data Space Alternative

Data Space Connectors and Federated Catalogue

Obstacle

The core concept of the GDDS is to allow the sharing of protected datasets, in the form of assets, among a set of trusted participants. The GDDS requires a federated system able to plug different participants into the data space. Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) is a potential solution that was tested and evaluated.

Solution

AD4GD implemented a Minimum Viable Dataspace with a Provider Data Connector instance to define and store assets, and a Consumer Data Connector instance to execute transaction and retrieve of assets. An implemented Federated Catalogue allows the registration of several related connectors, allowing data sharing among other registered partners thanks to specific adaptors that help to define and register different HTTP sources as EDC Assets.

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Description and usage

The Minimum Viable Dataspace deployed by AD4GD is based on the EDC components. The connectors are the central elements of the data space, providing secure, reliable, and structured data exchange between participants. They are easily manageable thanks to a set of user-friendly Web Data dashboards. The consumer backend extends the connector's data plane by allowing long term persistence of the assets into user's storage systems, such as MinIO. Secure and authenticated connections are ensured by an identify provider called DAPS, that functions as an Identity Access Management (IAM) layer, issuing Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT) to authenticated and verified participants. A Federated Catalogue works as a data broker by enabling participants to find and access data offerings published by others. The final demonstrator,

includes 5 participant nodes, each acting as a consumer and provider, from 2 different projects (AD4GD and FAIRiCUBE).

Foreseen applications

The Prototype of the GDDS and the Federated Data Catalogue have already been leveraged by THE AD4GD sister projects. Its architecture and components will be exploited as a foundational asset into the SAGE project. The prototype will inform or be reused in other projects like CEADS, SusPot and cAgriLabs.

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Federated connectors' scenario.

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Green Deal Data Space Prototype

FACTS: Federated Agile Collaborative Trusted System

Obstacle

The Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (EDC) technology still faces several challenges, including issues related to GDPR compliance, especially with regard to the exchange of personal data in the context of contract negotiation and formalisation, as well as the weak resilience of the system due to its highly centralised structure, which creates single points of failure.

Solution

AD4GD proposes an alternative solution to the conventional approach proposed by IDSA that substitutes the need for Dataspace connectors in general and the EDC in particular. It is called FACTS and implements Integrity, Provenance, and Trust as essential elements of a resilient data service, offering significant value for both clients and services ensuring data reliability, traceability and trustworthiness.

Description

FACTS, was firstly demonstrated in the OGC Testbed 20 IPT (OGC, 2025) by Secure Dimensions. FACTS' architecture includes an Immutable Catalogue, based on blockchain technologies, and implemented based on the Open Source Hyperledger-Fabric project. It ensures that the metadata record representing an asset cannot be tempered with, and its integrity is preserved by calculating a hash with the actual data. To avoid complexity, FACTS offers an STAC interface where assets in the blockchain are presented as resources in API-accessible collections.

FACTS also implements smart certificates issued by entrusted entities, that can be considered contracts between the user and the data producer. Unlike the IDSA approach, these certificates are prenegotiated with the entrusted issues and stored in the user wallet, instead of in the EDC, avoiding any personal data flow. Certificates can be revoked or limited to data processing, ensuring sovereignty.

Use in the project

FACTS was implemented by Secure Dimensions as part of an exploratory subcontract that CREAM had with them in the AD4GD project, and in the context of OGC's activities where the project participated.

Foreseen applications

After experimenting and demonstrating with FACTS, AD4GD believes that FACTS could serve as a federated alternative to the traditional Dataspace infrastructures more respectful with GDPR.

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TAPIS, an API Explorer and Table Manager

Obstacle

Working with standard APIs is highly useful when handling collections of observations from IoT sensors, satellite imagery and citizen science. However, in the absence of dedicated tools, they can be challenging to work with. Such tools remained scarce, and no solution existed for simply exploring data streams, parties, or observations.

Solution

AD4GD deployed TAPIS, a visual interface based on tables as internal data structure that allows users to easily manage different standard APIs and data file formats. It enables chained node-edge operations, allowing users to interactively design, save and reuse data workflows. TAPIS does not need any installation as it functions directly in the browser, becoming a practical tool to perform interoperability tests.

Description

TAPIS is a lightweight multipurpose tool that can explore APIs and services such as STA, STApplus, S3, Eclipse Data Space Connector, CSW and OGC API collections, features, records and STAC. Positioned between URL-based tools and domain-specific GUIs, it is ideal for interoperability testing. TAPIS supports direct reading of CSV, DBF, GeoPackage, JSON, JSON-LD and GeoJSON file formats. It offers robust table editing and semantical enrichment capabilities, along with data visualization options, including bar charts, pie charts, scatter plots, and maps. TAPIS is integrated with MiraMon Map Browser and its Geospatial User Feedback system (NiMMbus).

Usage in the project

TAPIS has served as a single client tool to connect different services that usually require

separated tools, and to extract the data in a table form. It has also been essential for testing the interoperability of the project components and its protocols, ensuring that they can be used seamlessly together.

Foreseen applications

TAPIS can be exploited by public servants, scientists, teachers or companies interested in learning about API interactions, seeking data access or generally handling environmental and sensor data.

Try it: www.tapis.grumets.cat

References

- <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-TAPIS>
- Bastin, L., Kriukov, V., Lush, V., Serral, I., Hodson, T., Borger, C., & Zamzow, M. (2025). AD4GD D6.2. Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment Report. Zenodo.

Conclusions

AD4GD demonstrated how to deploy a modern, decentralized and useful set of components for the Green Deal Data Space in the cloud. In AD4GD, components exchange information using a set of protocols and OGC APIs such as SensorThings API and OGC API Coverages. Since the components deployed by AD4GD should exchange information with other infrastructures part of the GDDS, the data has been harmonized and semantically enriched ensuring that other recipients in the GDDS are able to understand the variables observed by using Essential Variables dictionary stored in the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM) and exposed through the OGC RAINBOW. Some AI and ML processing chain were deployed for the benefit of three practical pilots on water

quality, biodiversity connectivity and air quality. The results were exposed using International Data Space Association standards and also implemented in SIMPL. Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (EDC), that implement the Data Space Protocols, were deployed by AD4GD, USAGE and FAIRiCUBE, thus forming a 3-node GDDS to exchange data among projects, allowing secured file exchange as well as access to OGC APIs queries. It is expected that these 3 EDC nodes as well as the semantic uplift mechanism constitute the embryo of a future GDDS that project SAGE should deploy in the next 2.5 years. Additionally, the AD4GD explored alternative solutions for exchange of restricted data in a data space such as FACTS smart certificates for immutable assets.

The project defined FAIR and open principles and licences ensuring maximum reusability of other components such as TAPIS, STA importers, Open Data Cube coverage access, etc (already reused in more4nature and CitiObs projects).

In conclusion, by combining robust technical innovations, international standards, data space protocols, and inclusive and clear IPR framework, AD4GD created a strong foundation for a practical and lasting contribution to the GDDS and wider environmental data ecosystems.

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